

S-Module

**Characterization of CRISPR/Cas9 *HMA4* mutants in
*Arabidopsis halleri***

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Bochum, March 2021

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperaccumulation is a process that gives plants the ability to grow on soil or water that is contaminated with high concentrations of metals. High metal concentrations are toxic to plants that are not capable of hyperaccumulation contrary to non-hyperaccumulators, they extract the metals at a higher rate through root-to-shoot translocation by mediating xylem loading in the roots and intercellular distribution in leaves (Krämer 2010). These plants are of interest to rehabilitate contaminated ecosystems by extracting the metals out of the soil. They also could be harvested and used as a metal provider (Rascio & Navari-Izzo 2011).

Some species of the *Brassicaceae* family are metal hyperaccumulators as for example *Arabidopsis halleri*. Microarray-based comparisons were used to identify candidate genes that might be responsible for hyperaccumulation or hypertolerance. A higher expression of these genes in the known hyperaccumulator *A. halleri* compared to *A. thaliana* hints to functional relevance during these processes (Talke et al. 2006).

One of the candidates was the heavy metal ATPase 4 (*HMA4*) which encodes for a zinc/cadmium transporting P_{1B}-type heavy-metal ATPase (Axelsen & Palmgren 2001). P_{1B}-type heavy metal ATPases (HMAs) are transmembrane metal-transporting proteins that play a key role in the metal homeostasis of plants. *HMA4* is expressed in the pericycle and the xylem parenchyma to load zinc and cadmium in the apoplastic pathway which enables the metals to reach the shoots through the transpiration stream (Krämer 2010). *A. halleri* possesses peculiar triplication of *HMA4* located on a chromosomal segment spanned about 150 base pairs (Talke et al. 2006).

One tool to determine the gene function is to generate RNAi lines (RNA interference). This is a naturally occurring mechanism in eukaryotic cells to silence specific genes. Short interfering RNAs interact with mRNAs and then get targeted and degraded by enzymes. The RNAi system can be used to generate transgenic lines with a significantly reduced expression of the gene of interest. These mutants are functionally close to a real knockout but a total suppression of the target gene cannot be achieved. Knockout strains in which the expression of a gene is entirely eliminated could provide better results for a better understanding of the function of particular genes.

For given reasons CRISPR/Cas9 should be established as a method for creating stable knockout mutants with the aim to silence all three copies of *HMA4*.

CRISPR/Cas (**C**lustered **R**egularly **I**nterspaced **S**hort **P**alindromic **R**epeats/**C**RISPR-**a**ssociated Protein) is a method that is used to cut DNA at specific locations. Genes can be removed or deactivated with the CRISPR/Cas system. Originally this mechanism is used by bacteria as adaptive antiviral defense mechanism. The DNA cutting DNA endonuclease enzyme, Cas, binds a specific RNA sequence followed by another RNA sequence that is bound to a complementary DNA sequence. The RNA functions as a bridge between Cas and the DNA that is cut. The complex of Cas, RNA and DNA allows the site directed endonuclease activity of Cas resulting in a double strand break. During the cells inherent repair mechanisms by non-homologous end joining, a loss of several base pairs is highly probable, effectively leading to deletions of targeted sequences. To introduce new DNA, ends that are complementary to the cut sequence are required.

For the creation of triple *HMA4* mutants in *A. halleri* two different targets were used. They are complementary to the first exon of each *HMA4* copy and due to their position result in a deletion of 26 bp or even the whole *HMA4* locus (Figure 1).

Genomischer *HMA4*-Lokus in *A. halleri*

Exon 1

Figure 1: Overview about the sgRNA binding sites in different *HMA4* genes of *Arabidopsis halleri*.

This construct contains two sgRNAs with the targets 2(*HMA4-2*) and 3(*HMA4-3*). The construct contains two sgRNAs complementary to the first exon of each *HMA4* copy to guide the Cas9-Endonuclease to the desired position.

In a previous study therefore several *HMA4* mutant lines were designed. Out of these lines ten independent calli were generated and cloned. Sublines were generated out of plant tissues to isolate and generate coherent mutant sublines. The target of this module was to analyze and characterize the genotype of these *HMA4* mutant sublines.

2. METHODS

2.1 Plant material

As plant material, *AhHMA4* sterile mutant lines of *A. halleri* were used. The generation of these mutants was performed by Dr. Ines Kubigsteltig (12/2015) and Simon Brückner (01/2016). Originally ten independent calli were generated from which the lines 1 to 10 emerged. The generation of the subclones is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: First transformation round of *A. halleri* *HMA4* mutant lines.

A detailed description about how the cloning, plant transformation and plant propagation can be found in the final report (Kubigsteltig and Brückner, 2017).

As a first step, shoots and roots were harvested from each independent transgenic line (Table 1) separately. Several samples from shoots were taken to isolate genomic DNA and RNA, respectively. The samples were frozen with liquid nitrogen and kept at -80°C until use.

Table 1: Transgenic lines created to establish CRISPR/Cas9 mutants. Lines which were used are sorted by transformation round. *c/c* = Crispr/Cas9, Kallus I,II,III = Regeneration lines

Transformation round 1	Transformation round 2
1.2 <i>c/c</i>	4.1 <i>c/c</i>
1.4 <i>c/c</i>	4.2 <i>c/c</i>
1.4 Kallus II	5.1 <i>c/c</i>
1.4 Kallus III	5.1 Kallus
1.4 Kallus IV	5.2 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.1 (Kallus) <i>c/c</i>	5.4 Kallus (Erde)
1.4.1 Kallus II	6.2 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.2 (Kallus) <i>c/c</i>	8.1 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.2 Kallus I	8.2 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.2 Kallus II	9.1 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.3 (Kallus) <i>c/c</i>	9.2 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.4 (Kallus) <i>c/c</i>	10.1 <i>c/c</i>
1.4.4 Kallus	10.2 <i>c/c</i>
3a <i>c/c</i>	

2.2 Genotyping of *A. halleri* HMA4 mutants

2.2.1 DNA isolation of *A. halleri* HMA4 mutants

To genotype the *AhHMA4* mutant lines, genomic DNA was isolated from shoots of each mutant line (Table 1). As a control, wild type plants of *A. halleri* were used. The shoot tissue was grinded with plastic pestles in Eppendorf tubes and 400 µl Edward buffer was added followed by vortexing and centrifuging (3 min, 14000 rpm). Afterwards 300 µl of the supernatant was taken and transferred to a new sample tube and 300 µl isopropanol was added. Subsequently the samples were centrifuged (5 min, 14000 rpm), the supernatant was carefully removed and the pellets were air dried. Lastly the samples were resuspended in 25 µl T0.1E buffer.

Buffers:

<u>Edward buffer</u>	<u>T0.1E buffer</u>
200 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5	10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0
250 mM NaCl	0.1 mM EDTA
25 mM EDTA pH 8.0	
0.5% SDS	

2.2.2 Polymerase chain reaction

The DNA was amplified via polymerase chain reaction. The standard pcr-mix (20 µl) contained the following: 10 µl DreamTaq 2x (Thermo Fischer Scientific), 1 µl primer forward, 1 µl primer reverse, 1 µl gDNA, 7 µl milli-Q water.

The polymerase chain reaction conditions were as following:

1. Initial denaturation	95°C	3 min
2. Denaturation	95°C	30 s
3. Hybridisation	43°C	30 s
4. Elongation	72°C	45 s
2.-4. Repetition		34x
5. Final elongation	72°C	2 min

Primer & PCR-Products:

<u>Nr.</u>	<u>Oligonucleotide</u>	<u>Sequence 5'-3'</u>
1	AhHMA4-1-anti	AAGTGACTTGTTGGATCACATATTTTAC
2	AhHMA4-2-anti2	CGAAACCATTAATTTAATATTCTCTCC
3	AhHMA4-3-anti	TGTTGGATTAATGACCAACAAGTAA
4	HMA4-universal-sense	AGTGAAGAAGTTGCAAAAGAGTTAC
11	pHMA4-1-sense	CAAAAGCCTATAAATCAATATAATTTG

<u>Primer sense/anti</u>	<u>Amplification</u>	<u>PCR product [bp]</u>
11/1	<i>A.h.</i> HMA4-1 (new)	478
4/2	<i>A.h.</i> HMA4-2	378
4/3	<i>A.h.</i> HMA4-3	356
11/2	<i>A.h.</i> hma4-(Δ 1-2)	466
11/3	<i>A.h.</i> hma4-(Δ 1-3)	444

2.2.3 DNA agarose gel electrophoresis

The results of the polymerase chain reaction were analyzed via agarose gel electrophoresis. Therefore a 1.5% agarose gel was made by boiling up agarose in 1x TAE buffer. Additionally 5% ethidium bromide was added as nucleic acid stain. After the gel hardened, the samples were loaded and the gel was running at a tension of 135 Volt for 30 minutes. Lastly the gel was illuminated with ultraviolet light to make the DNA bands visible. As marker a 1 kb DNA Ladder (New England BioLabs) was used.

Buffers:

<u>50x TAE buffer</u>	<u>TAE buffer</u>
242 g Tris	20 ml 50x TAE buffer
100 ml Na ₂ EDTA (0.5 M, pH 8.0)	Ad 1000 ml ddH ₂ O
51,1 ml Acetic acid	
Ad 1000 ml ddH ₂ O	

2.2.4 Purification of PCR products

The purification of the PCR products was carried out with the *QIAEX II Gel Extraction Kit* from QIAGEN following manufacturers instructions.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Genotyping of *A. halleri* *HMA4* mutants via polymerase chain reaction.

Firstly, the primers from the laboratory stock were tested for usage. The specificity of the primers was tested in earlier studies (Kubigsteltig und Brückner, 2017). For the copies of *HMA4-2* and *HMA4-3* no specific sense primer could be designed. Therefore, the universal binding *HMA4*-universal-sense primer was used together with a specific antisense primer to genotype all *HMA4* mutant sublimes shown in Table 1.

Figure 3: Used primer combinations for different *HMA4* copies.

To continue the genotyping, the PCR products were further analyzed via DNA agarose electrophoresis. The results are shown in the following figures.

pHMA4-1 sense – AhHMA4-2-anti2

Figure 4: Example of PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant (samples 141-162 and wild-type). The primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-2)*. Samples are referred as in table 1. B: Blank.

pHMA4-1 sense – AhHMA4-3-anti

Figure 5: Same conditions as presented in Figure 4.

pHMA4-1 sense – AhHMA4-1-anti

Figure 6: Same conditions as presented in Figure 4.

HMA4-universal-sense – AhHMA4-2-anti2

Figure 7: Same conditions as presented in Figure 4.

HMA4-universal-sense – AhHMA4-3-anti

Figure 8: Same conditions as presented in Figure 4.

The genotyping analysis of the other lines listed in Table 1 was performed as stated above. The results are summarized in Table 2. The X means there was a band detected in the PCR analysis.

Table 2: PCR analysis results of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutants and wild-type.

ID	Sample name	HMA4-1 WT	HMA4-2 WT	HMA4-3 WT	Δ1-2	Δ1-3
1	1.4 c/c	X	X	-	-	X
3	1.4 c/c	X	X	-	-	X
5	1.4 c/c	X	X	-	-	X
8	1.2 c/c	-	-	-	-	-
10	1.2 c/c	X	-	-	-	-
12	1.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	X

15	1.4.1 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	-	-	-
17	1.4.1 (Kallus) c/c	-	X	-	-	-
19	1.4.1 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	-	-	-
22	1.4.2 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	-	-	-
24	1.4.2 (Kallus) c/c	-	X	-	-	-
26	1.4.2 (Kallus) c/c	X	-	-	-	-
29	1.4.3 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	-	-
31	1.4.3 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	X	-
33	1.4.3 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	X	-
36	1.4.4 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	X	-
38	1.4.4 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	-	-
40	1.4.4 (Kallus) c/c	X	X	X	X	-
43	3a c/c	X	X	X	X	-
45	3a c/c	X	X	-	-	-
47	3a c/c	X	X	-	-	-
50	4.1 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
52	4.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
54	4.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
57	4.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
59	4.2 c/c	X	X	X	-	-
61	4.2 c/c	X	X	X	X	-
64	5.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
66	5.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
68	5.1 c/c	X	X	X	X	-
71	5.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
73	5.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
75	5.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
78	6.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
80	6.2 c/c	X	-	-	X	-
82	6.2 c/c	X	-	-	-	-
85	8.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-

87	8.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
89	8.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
92	8.2 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
94	8.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
96	8.2 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
99	9.1 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
101	9.1 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
103	9.1 c/c	-	-	-	-	-
106	9.2 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
108	9.2 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
110	9.2 c/c	-	X	-	-	-
113	10.1 c/c	-	X	-	-	-
115	10.1 c/c	X	X	-	X	-
117	10.1 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
120	10.2 c/c	X	X	X	X	-
122	10.2 c/c	X	X	-	-	-
124	10.2 c/c	X	X	X	X	-
127	1.4 Kallus II c/c	X	X	X	X	-
129	1.4 Kallus II c/c	X	X	X	X	-
131	1.4 Kallus II c/c	X	X	X	X	-
134	1.4 Kallus III c/c	X	X	X	X	-
136	1.4 Kallus III c/c	X	X	X	X	-
138	1.4 Kallus III c/c	-	X	X	X	-
141	1.4.1 Kallus I c/c	X	X	-	-	-
143	1.4.1 Kallus I c/c	X	X	X	X	-
145	1.4.1 Kallus I c/c	X	X	X	X	-
148	1.4.1 Kallus II c/c	X	X	X	X	-
150	1.4.1 Kallus II c/c	X	X	-	X	-
152	1.4.1 Kallus II c/c	X	X	-	X	-

155	1.4.2 Kallus I c/c	X	X	X	X	-
157	1.4.2 Kallus I c/c	X	X	-	-	-
159	1.4.2 Kallus I c/c	X	X	X	X	-
162	1.4.2 Kallus II c/c	X	X	X	X	-
164	1.4.2 Kallus II c/c	X	X	-	X	-
166	1.4.2 Kallus II c/c	X	X	-	X	-
169	5.1 Kallus c/c	X	X	-	-	-
171	5.1 Kallus c/c	X	X	-	-	-
173	5.1 Kallus c/c	X	X	-	-	-
176	WT A	X	X	-	-	-
178	WT A	X	X	-	-	-
180	WT A	X	X	-	-	-
183	WT B	X	X	-	-	-
185	WT B	X	X	X	-	-
187	WT B	X	X	X	-	-
190	WT C	-	X	X	-	-
192	WT C	X	X	X	-	-
195	WT C	X	X	-	-	-

To identify the presence of a deletion in the *HMA4* mutant sublines, two different primer combinations were used. The first primer combination is pHMA4-1-sense and AhHMA4-2-anti2 to identify a deletion between *HMA4-1* and *HMA4-2*, with an expected PCR product of 466 base pairs. The second primer combination is pHMA4-1-sense and AhHMA4-3-anti to identify a deletion between *HMA4-1* and *HMA4-3*, with an expected PCR product of 444 base pairs. The exact localization of the deleted parts is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Verification of the deletions at the *HMA4* loci. Due to the use of a specific primer that binds at the promotor region of the *HMA4-1* gene with the matching antisense primer of *HMA4-2* and *HMA4-3*, PCR products can only be expected if the deletion was correct.

The results are shown in Table 2 in the column $\Delta 1-2$ and $\Delta 1-3$. The columns *HMA4-1*, *HMA4-2* and *HMA4-3* show results of the amplification of the wild type *HMA4* copies with specific primers for each *HMA4* copy (1,2,3). The PCR analysis shows that deletions at the location of *HMA4* are common in various plant lines but not in every cell. The most promising lines are 1.4.3 (Kallus) c/c, 1.4.4 (Kallus) c/c, 1.4.1 Kallus I c/c, 1.4 Kallus II, 1.4 Kallus III and 1.4.2 Kallus I c/c. They showed the most intense bands in almost all samples for the deletions. The lines 1.4.1 (Kallus) c/c, 1.4.2 (Kallus) c/c, 5.2 c/c and 8.1 c/c showed no deletion in any sample.

4. DISCUSSION

The goal of this project was to further analyse the *HMA4* CRISPR/Cas9 transgenic lines in *A. halleri* generated previously in the department of Prof. Ute Krämer (Brückner 2017). In the previous work of Dr. Ines Kubigsteltig and Simon Brückner various transgenic lines with target specific deletions in the *HMA4* gene copies were successfully produced. This work was focused on genotyping further the transgenic lines to identify homozygous transgenic plants. Some plants showed partially deletions at the location of the *HMA4* alleles in the cells, but not in all. Even though the ratio and amount of cells with mutated *HMA4* is higher than before, the wild type *HMA4* copies are still detectable. Therefore, no homozygous lines were generated yet. To reach this, further investigation of missing wild type *HMA4* genes needs to be done to identify the homozygous *HMA4* mutant plants and continuously propagation through calli regeneration. Interestingly, compared to previous work the *HMA4* transgenic bands were detected in the first PCR amplification and were relatively high in intensity in comparison to the previous study. Due to nature of the mutagenesis via Cas9 the process can continue and it is to expect that more deletions will occur as stated in the previous study in which they had to amplify the genes a second time via PCR because no bands were detected at the first time. Afterwards calli out of leaf tissues were generated out of the most promising lines and were analyzed in this module.

Since *A. halleri* is a plant that is really hard to propagate with classic genetic methods like homologous recombination, calli have to be generated through tissues of plants with already high amounts of deletions at the *HMA4* alleles. The best candidates for further propagation in future projects are 1.4.3 (Kallus) *c/c*, 1.4.4 (Kallus) *c/c*, 1.4.1 Kallus I *c/c*, 1.4 Kallus II, 1.4 Kallus III and 1.4.2 Kallus I *c/c*, since they showed the highest amount of deletions of all analyzed plants.

5. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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6. APPENDIX

6.1 Genotyping of *A. halleri* HMA4 mutants via polymerase chain reaction.

Samples 1-22

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 1-22. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-2)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 1-22. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-3)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 1-22. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-1*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 1-22. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-2.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 1-22. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-3.

Samples 24-45

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 24-45. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-2).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 24-45. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-3)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 24-45. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-1*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 24-45. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-2*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 24-45. Primers 4 and 3 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-3

Samples 47-68

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 47-68. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-2).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 47-68. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-3).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 47-68. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-1.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 47-68. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-2.

Samples 71-92

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 71-92. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-2).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 71-92. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-1.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 71-92. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-2.

Samples 94-115

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 94-115. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-2).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 94-115. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-3)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 94-115. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-1*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 94-115. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-2*.

Samples 117-138

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 117-138. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-2)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 117-138. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-3)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 117-138. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-1*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 117-138. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-2.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 117-138. Primers 4 and 3 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-3.

Samples 164-173

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 164-173. Primers 11 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. hma4-(Δ 1-2).

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 164-173. Primers 11 and 3 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. hma4-(Δ1-3)*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 164-173. Sample 176 is a wild type control. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-1*.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 deletion mutant samples 164-173. Sample 176 is a wild type control. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of *A.h. HMA4-2*.

Samples wild type

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 wild type samples 1: 176, 2: 178, 3: 180, 4: 183, 5: 185, 6: 187, 7: 190, 8: 192, 9: 195. Primers 11 and 1 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-1.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 wild type samples 1: 176, 2: 178, 3: 180, 4: 183, 5: 185, 6: 187, 7: 190, 8: 192, 9: 195. Primers 4 and 2 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-2.

PCR analysis of *A. halleri* HMA4 wild type samples 1: 176, 2: 178, 3: 180, 4: 183, 5: 185, 6: 187, 7: 190, 8: 192, 9: 195. Primers 4 and 3 were used for a specific detection of A.h. HMA4-3.